

EFFECTIVE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH CONSIDERING INTERFACIAL THERMAL RESISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the degree of the effect of the interfacial thermal resistance, we developed new simulation code which can calculate the effective thermal conductivity of composites with considering the interfacial thermal resistance. Size, volume fraction and distribution of the reinforcement and the element size were varied, and series of calculations for aluminum-carbon composites were carried out. The critical element size was defined by a simple equation in this study. This critical element size is important value to design composites. If the size of the reinforcement is smaller than the critical element size, it is predicted that the effective thermal conductivity will decrease by the interfacial thermal resistance. On the other hand, if the size of the reinforcement is large enough, the effective thermal conductivity will not decrease.

1 INTRODUCTION

The interfacial thermal resistance between the matrix and the reinforcement is thought to have a considerable effect on the effective thermal conductivity of composites. In order to predict the effective thermal conductivity of composites, many theoretical or empirical models have been proposed [1-5]. The finite volume method is considered one of the most promising methods for studying the effective thermal conductivity of composites. Haitao et al. [6] calculated the interfacial thermal resistance by phonon diffuse mismatch model [7].

To investigate the degree of the effect of the interfacial thermal resistance, we developed new simulation code which can calculate the effective thermal conductivity of composites with considering the interfacial thermal resistance. Size, volume fraction and distribution of reinforcement and element size were varied, and series of calculation were carried out.

2 CALCULATION PROCEDURE

Finite volume method was used to calculate two-dimensional temperature distributions. Temperature of element i, j after Δt , $T_{i,j}^{n+1}$, can be calculated by

$$T_{i,j}^{n+1} = T_{i,j}^n + \frac{\Delta t}{\rho c} \left(\frac{q_{i+1,j}^n - q_{i-1,j}^n}{\Delta x} + \frac{q_{i,j+1}^n - q_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $T_{i,j}^n$ is the present temperature of the noticed element i, j , Δx and Δy are size of element, ρ is

density and c is specific heat. When the heat move by heat conduction between elements, heat flux q^n is calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} q_{i+1,j}^n &= \lambda_{i+\frac{1}{2},j} \left(\frac{T_{i+1,j}^n - T_{i,j}^n}{\Delta x} \right), & q_{i-1,j}^n &= \lambda_{i-\frac{1}{2},j} \left(\frac{T_{i,j}^n - T_{i-1,j}^n}{\Delta x} \right), \\ q_{i,j+1}^n &= \lambda_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{T_{i,j+1}^n - T_{i,j}^n}{\Delta y} \right), & q_{i,j-1}^n &= \lambda_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{T_{i,j}^n - T_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $T_{i+1,j}^n$, $T_{i-1,j}^n$, $T_{i,j+1}^n$ and $T_{i,j-1}^n$ is temperature of neighbor elements. When the type of a neighbor element is different from the noticed elements, harmonic mean of thermal conductivity is used and calculated by

$$\lambda_{i+\frac{1}{2},j} = \frac{2\lambda_{i,j}\lambda_{i+1,j}}{\lambda_{i,j} + \lambda_{i+1,j}}, \lambda_{i-\frac{1}{2},j} = \frac{2\lambda_{i,j}\lambda_{i-1,j}}{\lambda_{i,j} + \lambda_{i-1,j}}, \lambda_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{2\lambda_{i,j}\lambda_{i,j+1}}{\lambda_{i,j} + \lambda_{i,j+1}}, \lambda_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{2\lambda_{i,j}\lambda_{i,j-1}}{\lambda_{i,j} + \lambda_{i,j-1}}. \quad (3)$$

where λ_{ij} is thermal conductivity of noticed element and $\lambda_{i+1,j}$, $\lambda_{i-1,j}$, $\lambda_{i,j+1}$ and $\lambda_{i,j-1}$ is thermal conductivity of a neighbor element. When the type of a neighbor element is different from the noticed elements and the heat move by heat transfer between elements, heat flux q^n is calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} q_{i+1,j}^n &= h(T_{i+1,j} - T_{i,j}), & q_{i-1,j}^n &= h(T_{i,j} - T_{i-1,j}), \\ q_{i,j+1}^n &= h(T_{i,j+1} - T_{i,j}), & q_{i,j-1}^n &= h(T_{i,j} - T_{i,j-1}), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where h is the coefficient of heat transfer between different materials.

Fig. 1 shows schematics of simulation model. Composite part is sandwiched by heat sources. The size of composite part was 100×100 elements, and the size of heat sources was 5×100 elements. The size of each element was varied from 1×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-9} [m]. Thermal conductivity of aluminum matrix, λ_{Al} , was set to 236.0 [W/m · K] and that of reinforcing carbon, λ_C was set to 1200.0 [W/m · K]. Coefficient of heat transfer at the interface between aluminum and carbon, h_{Al-C} , was set to 110113846.7 [W/m² · K][6]. Temperature of all elements was set to 300 [K] as initial condition and boundary condition was set to approach temperature gradient of 4.5454×10^4 [K/m]. Temperature was iteratively updated until average variation of temperature of each element was lower than 10^{-14} , and steady state of temperature distributions was obtained. Effective thermal conductivity of composite, λ_{eff} , was evaluated from steady state of temperature distributions using following equation.

$$\lambda_{eff} = \frac{\lambda_{Al} \Delta T_{12} N_x}{\Delta T_{LR} + N_L \Delta T_{12} - N_R \Delta T_{12}}, \quad (5)$$

where ΔT_{LR} is temperature difference between left and right side and ΔT_{12} is the average of temperature difference between first and second column. N_L and N_R are number of elements of right and left heat source, respectively. N_x is number of elements of composite part.

Figure 1: Schematics of simulation model.

Two kinds of arrangement of reinforcements were assumed in this study as shown in Fig. 2. The first row of the figure represents a fibrous reinforcement arranged in perpendicular to heat flux. The second row of the figure represents granuloise reinforcements arranged in uniform random arrangement. The size of particles was constant, and volume fraction was varied with changing the number of particles.

Figure 2: Arrangement of reinforcement.

3 RESULTS

3.1 The effective thermal conductivity with a fibrous reinforcement

Fig. 3 shows the simulation results in which the fibrous reinforcement are arranged in perpendicular to heat flux. Fig. 3(a) shows relationship between volume fraction and effective thermal conductivity when the heat assumes to move by heat conduction at the interface between matrix and reinforcements. Solid line indicates the effective thermal conductivity, λ_{eff} , calculated by rule of mixture (ROM),

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{eff}} = \frac{V}{\lambda_c} + \frac{1-V}{\lambda_{Al}}, \quad (6)$$

where V is volume fraction of reinforcement. The effective thermal conductivities calculated by computer simulation agree with equation (6) in each volume fraction. This means that evaluation method of the effective thermal conductivity which was employed in this study is valid. Closed circles, squares, diamonds, triangles and crosses in the figure indicates elements sizes (1×10^{-9} to 1×10^{-3} [m]), and the effective thermal conductivities is not changed even if the element size is changed. In other words, the element size does not affect the effective thermal conductivity when the heat assumes to move by heat conduction at the interface. In contrast, as shown in Fig. 3(b), the effective thermal conductivities decrease with decreasing the element size when the heat assumes to move by heat transfer at the interface.

Fig. 4(a) shows relationship between element size and effective thermal conductivity when the heat assumes to move by heat conduction at the interface. The element size does not affect the effective thermal conductivity. In contrast, as shown in Fig. 4(b), the element size affect the effective thermal conductivity when the heat assumes to move by heat transfer at the interface. When element size is larger than 1×10^{-5} [m], the effective thermal conductivity is constant value at each volume fraction. However, when element size is smaller than 1×10^{-6} [m], the effective thermal conductivity begins to be affected and decrease due to the interfacial thermal resistance between the matrix and the reinforcement. This resistance affects most strongly when the element size is 1×10^{-9} [m].

Figure 3: Relationship between volume fraction and the effective thermal conductivity in which the fibrous reinforcement are arranged in perpendicular to heat flux, (a) considering heat conduction at the interface and (b) considering heat transfer at the interface.

Figure 4: Relationship between element size and the effective thermal conductivity in which the fibrous reinforcement are arranged in perpendicular to heat flux, (a) considering heat conduction at the interface and (b) considering heat transfer at the interface.

Fig 5 shows temperature decrease rate, R_i , which is calculated by dividing average temperature of i -th element column by temperature difference of both sides and represented by

$$R_i = \frac{1}{\Delta T_{LR} N_y} \sum_{j=0}^{N_y} T_{i,j}. \quad (7)$$

Fig. 5(a) shows the profile of the temperature decrease rate when the heat assumes to move by heat conduction at the interface. Blue, green and red line indicates the difference of element sizes, and the element size does not affect this profile. The arrows in the figure indicates positions of the interface between matrix and reinforcement. The slope at the part of the reinforcement is gentler than that of the matrix because the thermal conductivity of carbon is higher than that of aluminum. In contrast, as shown in Fig. 5(b), the element size affect the profile of the temperature decrease rate when the heat assumes to move by heat transfer at the interface. The gap of temperature begins to appear at the interface when element size is smaller than 1×10^{-6} [m]. This gap supposes to cause the decrease of the effective thermal conductivity of the composites. In other words, the interfacial thermal resistance between the matrix and the reinforcement can be explained by this gap.

Figure 5: The profile of the temperature decrease rate when the heat assumes to move (a) by heat conduction and (b) by heat transfer at the interface. The arrows indicates positions of the interface between matrix and reinforcement. The color of line indicates the difference of element sizes.

3.2 The effective thermal conductivity with granulose reinforcements

Fig. 6 shows the simulation results in which the granulose reinforcements arranged in uniform random arrangement. Fig. 6(a) shows relationship between element size and effective thermal conductivity at each volume fraction when the heat assumes to move by heat conduction at the interface. The element size does not affect the effective thermal conductivity. In contrast, as shown in Fig. 6(b), the element size affect the effective thermal conductivity when the heat assumes to move by heat transfer at the interface. The effective thermal conductivity continuously decreases with decreasing element size at each volume fraction. The effective thermal conductivity at the volume fraction of 0.5 with the element size of 1×10^{-3} [m] is remarkably above 700 [W/m · K] when considering heat transfer. In contrast, the effective thermal conductivity at the volume fraction of 0.5 is about 500 [W/m · K] when considering heat conduction. This large difference supposes to be explained by mechanism of heat transfer at the interface and density of the interfaces in the composites. The heat transfer mechanism at the interface will be discussed in the next section.

Figure 6: Relationship between element size and the effective thermal conductivity in which granulose reinforcements arranged in uniform random arrangement, (a) considering heat conduction at the interface and (b) considering heat transfer at the interface.

4 DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 7 shows schematics of heat flux at the interface between reinforcement and matrix. The heat flux which moves by heat conduction at the interface, q_{cond} , is calculated by

$$q_{cond} = \lambda \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta x}, \quad (8)$$

where λ is harmonic mean of thermal conductivity of the reinforcement and the matrix, ΔT is the temperature difference between P and Q and Δx is element size. On the other hand, the heat flux which moves by heat transfer at the interface, q_{tran} , is calculated by

$$q_{tran} = h\Delta T, \quad (9)$$

where h is the coefficient of heat transfer between the reinforcement and the matrix. When q_{tran} is smaller than q_{cond} , the heat flux is blocked and the gap of temperature appears at the interface. With this consideration, a simple equation,

$$\Delta x < \frac{\lambda}{h}, \quad (10)$$

can be derived. This equation means that the effective thermal conductivity starts to decrease due to the interfacial thermal resistance when the element size is smaller than λ / h . In addition, we define the critical element size as follows,

$$L_{cr} = \frac{\lambda}{h}. \quad (11)$$

Table. 1 shows the list of the critical element size which is calculated for aluminum-based composites. L_{cr} for Al-C composites is 3.58201×10^{-6} [m] and this value agrees with simulation results shown in Fig. 4(b). The critical element size is important to design composites. If the size of reinforcement is smaller than the critical element size, it is predicted that the effective thermal conductivity will decrease by the interfacial thermal resistance. On the other hand, if the size of reinforcement is large enough, the effective thermal conductivity will not decrease.

When q_{tran} is larger than q_{cond} , the heat moves excessively at the interface. This means that the thermal migration at the interface is faster than that in the matrix and the reinforcement. However, such kind of phenomena will not happen in practice. As shown in Fig. 6(b), the effective thermal conductivity when considering heat transfer at the interface was remarkably higher than that when considering heat conduction at the interface. The density of the interfaces is high in the higher volume fraction because there were many particles in the simulation cell as shown in the second row of Fig. 2. In addition, the large element size causes a condition of $q_{tran} > q_{cond}$. Therefore, high effective thermal conductivities were evaluated from the computer simulation, and this result seems to be artificial. It is necessary to pay attention when one selects simulation method to evaluate the effective thermal conductivity of composites. Simulation method with heat conduction at the interface should be selected if the element size is larger than the critical element size defined by equation (11). On the other hand, simulation method with heat transfer at the interface should be selected if the element size is smaller than the critical element size.

Figure 7: Schematics of heat flux at the interface between reinforcement and matrix.

Reinforce- ment	λ_{Al} [W/m · K]	λ_X [W/m · K]	λ_{Al-X} [W/m · K]	h_{Al-X} [W/m ² · K][6]	L_{cr} [m]
C(VGCF)	236	1200	394.429	110113846.7	3.58201×10^{-6}
SiC		270	251.8577	222728062.4	1.13079×10^{-6}
Si		168	196.2772	468353363.2	4.19079×10^{-7}
TiB ₂		100	140.4762	291188632.0	4.82423×10^{-7}
BN		50	82.51748	130892279.6	6.30423×10^{-7}
Al ₂ O ₃		30	53.23308	347844235.4	1.53037×10^{-7}
TiN		29	51.65283	433525385.1	1.19146×10^{-7}
ZnS		27.2	48.77812	859497881.3	5.67519×10^{-8}
ZnO		25.2	45.53752	1003088510.0	4.53973×10^{-8}
SiO ₂		8	15.47541	691323885.2	2.23852×10^{-8}

Table 1: List of the critical element size, L_{cr} . λ_{Al} and λ_X are thermal conductivity of the matrix and the reinforcement, respectively. λ_{Al-X} is harmonic mean of thermal conductivity of the reinforcement and the matrix. h_{Al-X} is the coefficient of heat transfer between the reinforcement and the matrix.

5 CONCLUSIONS

To investigate the degree of the effect of the interfacial thermal resistance, we developed new simulation code which can calculate the effective thermal conductivity of composites with considering the interfacial thermal resistance. Size, volume fraction and distribution of reinforcement and element size were varied, and series of calculation for aluminum-carbon composites were carried out. The critical element size, L_{cr} , is defined by a simple equation, $L_{cr} = \lambda / h$, where λ is the harmonic mean of thermal conductivity of the reinforcement and the matrix, and h is the coefficient of heat transfer between the reinforcement and the matrix. This critical element size is important value to design composites. If the size of reinforcement is smaller than the critical element size, it is predicted that the effective thermal conductivity will decrease by the interfacial thermal resistance. On the other hand, if the size of reinforcement is large enough, the effective thermal conductivity will not decrease.

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